

Characterization of Antimicrobial Peptide Produced by *Bacillus Subtilis* Subsp. *Subtilis*

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Research Article

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Abstract

Purpose:

Antimicrobial peptides are amongst the most promising class of peptides to contract the rise of global antimicrobial resistant. This article investigates a new antimicrobial peptide from bacteria.

Methods:

Bacterial identification was based on phenotypical and biochemical properties as well as 16S rRNA gene sequence homology. Bacterial growth and production of the inhibitory substance was standardized and optimized. The newly antimicrobial peptide was purified to homogeneity, subsequently analyzed by PAGE and MALDI-TOF-MS.

Results:

The bacterium identified as *Bacillus subtilis subsp. subtilis* and designated as strain MZ-32. Landy medium was best for the production when compared with different media after fixing the least influential variables in standardized fermentation conditions. Carbohydrate and nitrogen supplements investigated to improve production in Landy medium. The antimicrobial peptide of 2.158-Da was active against a broad range of skin-born pathogenic bacteria that were resistant to standard antibiotics, and possessed the physico-chemical properties of an ideal antimicrobial agent in terms of water solubility, thermal resistance, and stability towards acid/alkali (pH 4.0 to 9.0) treatments.

Conclusion:

The new strain and its associated peptide are potentially new candidates for medical and biotechnological applications.

Background

Peptide antibiotics are very diverse in their biochemical properties, molecular weights, inhibitory spectra and mechanisms of activity (Bin et al., 2021, Boparai et al., 2020). They incorporate unusual constituents like D-amino acids in their rigid, hydrophobic and/or cyclic structures that can synthesized ribosomally or non-ribosomally (Chen and Jiang 2023). Bacterial peptides may inhibit or kill other bacteria that are usually; but not always; closely related to the producer strain (Xuan et al., 2023). Peptides may exhibit one or more of antibacterial, fungicidal, anti-inflammatory, hemolytic, virucidal, antibiofilm, insecticidal and tumoricidal activities (Luo and Song, 2021; Stączek et al., 2023; Freitas et al., 2022). Based on their structural properties, these antimicrobial peptides can be grouped into three classes; peptides that are helicoidal, peptides containing one to several disulfide bridges and peptides rich in certain amino acids such as proline or tryptophan (Vaca et al., 2022). In recent years, the search for antibiotics has intensified in the light of the fact that the microbial resistance is continuously growing (Boparai and Sharma, 2023). Despite the wide variety of known antibiotics, less than 1% of antimicrobial agents have any medical or

commercial value (Luepke et al., 2017; Wright, 2016). The objective of the current study was to isolate, identify and determine the potential antagonistic activity of a newly isolated *Bacillus* strain from northern Pakistan. Data presented include the identification of producer strain and the successful purification and characterization of new antimicrobial peptide that is active against *Bacillus spp.* and other Gram-positive bacteria including pathogenic bacteria.

Materials and methods

Sample, media and reagents

Soil sample collected from roadside of Nathia-gali situated in northern Pakistan, in summer of 2006. Brain–heart infusion (BHI), trypticase soya broth (TSB), glucose broth [26], luria-bertani (LB) broth, nutrient broth (NB), pharmamedia (PM) (Alajlani et al., 2009) and Landy broth were used. The latter, modified by replacing carbohydrate and amino acid sources. All media, reagents, antibiotic discs and enzymes purchased from Oxoid, UK, except Pharmamedia obtained from Protein traders, USA.

Isolation of antimicrobial exhibiting bacteria

To screen for antagonistic bacteria, overlaid media plates were prepared using a thin layer of soft nutrient agar 0.8% seeded with test strains. Serial dilutions of the collected sample spread and incubated at 37°C for 12 to 24 h. Clear zones of inhibitions noted at lower dilutions. Among many isolates, strain MZ-32 inhibited the growth of the tested bacteria and considered for further analysis. Eventually strain MZ-32 collected from the reservoir plate and rechecked for activity and purity.

Antimicrobial activity assay

Culture supernatants of strain MZ-32 assayed for antimicrobial activity using agar-well diffusion method (Al-Ajlani et al., 2007). *Bacillus pamilus* used as test organism (50 µL, OD 0.3 at 600 nm). Arbitrary units (AU) per milliliter defined as the reciprocal of the greatest dilution of the supernatant that showed a zone of inhibition multiplied by 1000, divided by the volume of supernatant applied to the well.

Spectrum of activity

The following 58 different bacterial strains tested for their sensitivity using the agar-well diffusion assay: *Escherichia coli* C600, *Escherichia coli* DH5α1, *Bacillus subtilis* PY49, *Bacillus subtilis* 92, *Bacillus subtilis* 29, *Bacillus cereus* F, *Bacillus cereus* 92, *Bacillus fusiformis*, *Ochrobacterium intermedium* (our own lab. collection) and clinical isolates; 8 of *Klebsiella spp.* (from Children Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan), 1 of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 22 of *Staphylococcus aureus* and 18 of *Streptococcus pyogenes* (from Social Security Hospital, Lahore. Pakistan). The latter two were associated with secondary skin infections. Aliquots of an overnight culture of the bacteria assayed for sensitivity to the antibiotic added to sterile LB-broth blanks to yield a bacterial suspension with a final optical density of 0.5 at 600 nm. 500 µL of the bacterial suspension was gently mixed with soft agar and used in agar-well diffusion assay.

Fifty μ L culture supernatant obtained from incubation of producing strain at 37°C for 72 h with 120 rpm, was added into the well, zone of inhibition were observed and measured (Mohsin et al., 2018).

Table. 1

Bacterial identification

Identification of the isolated strain MZ-32 accomplished by combination of morphological and biochemical tests aided by the molecular characterization of 16S rDNA. PCR amplification of 16S rDNA successfully performed following the method described by Hasnain and Thomas 1996, with forward primer 27f (5-

AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG) and reverse primer 1522r (5-

AAGGAGGTGATCCA(AG)CCGCA). The purified 1.6 kb fragment was sequenced using an ABI Prism dye terminator cycle sequencing ready reaction kit and an ABI PRISM 377 DNA sequencer (Applied Biosystems). Analysis of DNA sequences were performed by using software ChromasPro version 1.34 (Technelysium Pty Ltd, Australia). Phylogenetic and molecular evolutionary analyses conducted using MEGA, version 3.1. The biochemical profile of test isolates was determined with the API 50 CHB strips following the manufacturer's instructions (bioMérieux, France). The results analyzed with the APILAB Plus software (bioMérieux, France).

Optimum production

Strain-29 grown in aerobic conditions at 37°C for 48 h in seven standard media to determine maximum product yield. Landy medium used to test the individual influence of different nitrogen and carbon supplements on the production (Fig. 2). Production conditions standardized by growing the bacterium at different temperatures (28, 35 and 42 °C), pH values (5, 6, 7, 8 and 9) and shaking settings (stationary, 70 and 140 rpm). After incubation of the producer strain under different conditions, each culture was centrifuged (2000 xg for 15 min) to remove the cells and tested for the variation in the inhibitory activity compared to their respective controls.

Product Preparation

To the culture filtrates, obtained from centrifuging (2000 xg for 15 min), an equal volume of chloroform was added (Al-Ajlani and Husnain, 2006). The separating funnel shaken well and left to clear turbidity. A thin layer of antimicrobial substances formed at the interface, which collected and redissolved in methanol acetonitrile (10:90 v/v).

Product Stability

Stability tests carried out using solution of TLC purified product. The solution contained at least 80000 AU/ml of activity against *B. fusiformis*. All treated samples and their replicas assayed in triplicates for residual activity using agar well diffusion method.

a. Enzymes

To determine the effects of enzymes (amylase, trypsin, proteinase, pronase, lipase and α amylase) on the inhibitory activity, product (18 μ L) was incubated with 2 μ L of each enzyme solutions [10 mg/ml in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0)] at 35°C for 6 and 12 h then boiled for 5 min.

b. Heat

For thermal stability, product solutions heated for 15 and 30 min at 80, 100 and 121°C.

c. pH

Effect of different pH values on AMS activity was determined by adding 10 μ L of the antibiotic solution to 90 μ L of distilled water adjusted to pH 2, 4, 7, 9 and 11 values with

HCl or NaOH.

Tricine-PAGE

Product analyzed and located by Tricine-PAGE [24] with an 18.5% acrylamide resolving gel. The gel was fixed in 20% isopropanol–10% acetic acid and washed in deionized water as described by Haider et al., 2019. The gel then placed in a Petri plate and overlaid with Muller Hinton soft agar containing a sensitive test organism.

Reverse Phase-HPLC and MALDI-TOF-MS

The product was subjected to further purification using reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with Thermo Hypersil-Keystone ODS (particle size, 5 μ m; column dimensions, 250 by 4.6 mm, Thermo Hypersil, USA). The sample was loaded onto the column with eluent A [0.1% (vol/vol) trifluoroacetic acid and 20% (vol/vol) acetonitrile] and eluted with segmented gradients of eluent B [0.1% (vol/vol) trifluoroacetic acid and 80% (vol/vol) acetonitrile]. The gradient comprised 40% eluent B for 30 min, followed by an increase to 100% eluent B over 10 min. The eluents A and B were prepared with Milli-Q HPLC grade water. The purified fractions were analyzed using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) to determine their molecular mass. Two microliters of the sample were mixed with 2 μ L of matrix solution (2 mg/mL of α -hydroxycinnamic acid in acetonitrile-methanol-water (1:1:1)) on the target plate. MALDI-TOF-MS spectra were recorded with a 337-nm nitrogen laser for desorption and ionization. The mass spectrometer was operated in the reflectron mode at an accelerating voltage of 18 kV with a 0.7 m ion flight path. The delay time was 375 ns, and matrix suppression was utilized. The mass spectra were averaged over 50 to 100 individual laser shots, and the laser intensity was set just above the threshold for ion production. External calibration was performed using the [M + H]⁺ signals of renin, adenocorticotrophic hormone, insulin oxidized B, and bovine insulin (Sigma-Aldrich Co.).

Results and Discussion

Isolation and identification of antimicrobial exhibiting bacteria

Among many strains exhibiting antimicrobial activity isolated, few were having intense activity against the tested clinical isolates. Isolate Mz-32 was one of the most active strains over many pathogenic test organisms. The strain was identified with morphological and biochemical tests accompanied by API 50 CHB and the sequence homology of 16S rRNA gene. Sequencing result of 16S rRNA was analyzed using NCBI web site. The result submitted to Genbank and accession no. DQ881707 obtained. Combinations of these tests lead to the confirmation of strains as *Bacillus subtilis subsp. subtilis*. The phylogenetic relationship of strain Mz-32 established with other related type *Bacillus* strains. Strain Mz-32 is available from Department of Microbiology and Molecular Genetics, University of the Punjab, Lahore.

Production of antibiotic

Almost all of inhibitory substances noted at exponential growth production of the strains. Maximum production corresponding to the highest suppression effect on the indicator organism obtained from three rich medium (BHI, LB and LN). Landy medium was showing higher production at lower cell concentration, indicating a potential medium for production. Landy medium selected for supplementation being a defined medium and as compared to the control, sucrose and arginine proved to be better source for carbon and nitrogen respectively for production of antibiotic. Interestingly, based on the cell growth and production relationship histidine and lactose produced higher production at lower cell concentration Fig. 1.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Inhibitory spectrum

Table 1 summarized the spectrum of activity against a panel of pathogenic and non-pathogenic test organisms. Pronounced activity observed over Gram-positive strains. The purified product demonstrated antagonistic activity against all the *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes* clinical isolates that did show resistance to standard antibiotics.

Table 1. Spectrum of activity: The zones of clearing ranged from nonexistent to a diameter of >20 mm.

Test organism	Average of activity expressed by diameter of inhibitory zone (mm)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> C600	10
<i>Escherichia coli</i> DH5a1	12
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> PY79	24
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> 92	32
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> 29	25
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> F	16
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> 92	20
<i>Bacillus fusiformis</i>	36
<i>Ochrobacterum intermedium</i>	Not detected
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp. (8 strains)	Not detected
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (22 strains)	26
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	16
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i> (18 strains)	22

Effect of enzymes, pH and heat on activity

The inhibitory activity not abrogated by trypsin, amylase and lipase; however, activity was affected by proteinase K (20% of residual activity). Inhibitory activity remained stable at 80°C for 30 min and reduced to 75.6% at 100°C but was completely lost at 121°C for 15 min. The activity was completely stable with minimum variation at pH 4 to 9 but drastically reduced at extreme pH values.

Analytical Characterization

Activity was detected on a wide spot corresponding to R_f 0.35 from a preparative TLC. This spot scratched and extracted with same elution solution A. The chromatogram of reverse phase-HPLC (Fig. 3a) showed the purification of the active spot R_f 0.35. Four active fractions were observed at 75% acetonitrile with retention time ranging from 7 to 8 min/ 3ml. However, maximum activity observed in fraction corresponding to retention time 7.556 min. This fraction further analyzed with MALDI-TOF MS and molecular mass was determined to be 2158-Da Fig. 3b. The molecular weight confirmed by running a bioassay test over tricine-PAGE.

Figure 3

Discussion

The widespread resistance of bacterial pathogens to conventional antibiotics has prompted renewed interest in the use of alternative natural microbial inhibitors such as antimicrobial peptides (Mba and Nweze, 2022). They have been mostly proposed as novel food preservatives (Kamal et al., 2023; Popa et al., 2022) but there is also interest in using them for the control of bacterial diseases in humans and animals (Ahmad et al., 2017) and even as biocontrol agents for plant diseases (Jaffar et al., 2023). *Bacillus* species produce a large number of peptide antibiotics of at least 25 different basic chemical structures (Kasper et al., 2019) representing a vast source of potentially useful products. The newly isolated strain MZ-32 reported in this investigation found to be taxonomically very close to *Bacillus subtilis subsp. subtilis*. The strain was able to produce an antimicrobial peptide that was inhibitory to the growth of common skin pathogens i.e. 22 strain of *Staphy. aureus* and 18 strains of *Strep. pyogenes* on an average of 26 and 22 mm respectively. In addition, the antimicrobial substance was able to inhibit two *Bacillus cereus* strains associated with food poisoning. As compared to standard antibiotics [Bacteriocin, Erythromycin, Cephadrin] the new peptide was very efficient with distinct activity in resistant cases. The maximum production noted using BHI and Landy medium, suggesting that biosynthesis of the inhibitory substance required a rich medium. Upon supplementing Landy medium with histidine and lactose, enhanced production obtained with no major increase in cell growth, indicating that these two supplements may be a part of the compound or essential components for the production of the bioactive compound. Sucrose and arginine did improve the growth and ultimately production. The antimicrobial substance was produced at the end of growth phase an indication that the inhibitory peptide is non-ribosomally synthesized (Gudiña et al., 2022). Nonribosomal peptides are structurally a very diverse family of natural products with an extremely broad range of biological activities and pharmacological properties (Walsh 2004). The proteinaceous nature of the isolated active compound was confirmed by its resistant to all tested enzymes except protease. Furthermore, the cyclic structure or the presence of unusual amino acids [36] may have contributed to the relative high resistance to proteases concentrations. The thermal and pH stability are both of great advantage to the antimicrobial peptide for possible medical or biotechnological uses. The exact size of the characterized peptide was determined to be 2152 m/z. This molecular weight did not match the m/z of iturins (1070.6 and 1092.6), fengycin (1435.8) and surfactin (1046.6) (Wan et al., 2022), bacillomycin D (1031.7), fengycin (1449.9), lacticin 481 (2902), subtilin (3319.4) and subtilosin A (3400.7) (Alajlani, 2022), ericin S (3442) and ericin A (2986), bacteriocin (960 to 983), bacteriocin (4893) and thuricin (3162) (Kaspar et al., 2019). The peptide did not match any of the antimicrobial peptides available at the antimicrobial peptide data base (<https://aps.unmc.edu/database>) leading to the conclusion that this peptide produced by *Bacillus subtilis subsp. subtilis* Mz-32 may represent a novel antibiotic with interesting properties to overcome increasing threats of microbial resistance.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

NA

Consent for publication

NA

Availability of data and materials

Contact the author

Competing interests

No competing interests in this article

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NA

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Lab member at Halle University, Halle and Microbiology and Molecular Genetics, Lahore.

Authors' information (optional)

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Figures

Figure 1

Influence of media supplemented with different nutrients on growth and inhibitory activity

Figure 2

Growth (line) and increase in production (bars) relationship, during fermentation in shake flask at 37 °C in Landy medium.

Figure 3

A. Reverse phase HPLC profiling, collected fractions were detected for activity B. Linear Mass spectrum of active purified product over a mass range 2000-2300